

A Fast TIFF File Value Extractor For Generating Timeseries Data to Enable Virtual Climate Stations

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Abstract—This paper presents a specialized C++ library that efficiently extracts values from TIFF files to allow for fast generation of timeseries information from a large set of GeoTIFF data. This was produced to assist in generating timeseries for the Hawai'i Climate Data Portal (HCDP), an online portal providing climatological data for the state of Hawai'i. The library utilizes a strip-oriented reading approach and a specialized LZW compression decoder that will process partial strips. A parallelized driver program was created to further enhance extraction efficiency for large sets of data. Experimental results demonstrate a significant speedup for extracting values in early columns from TIFF files. This library is integrated into an API backing the HCDP and is being leveraged to generate on-demand timeseries visualizations for climatological variables at arbitrary points throughout Hawai'i.

Index Terms—TIFF, GeoTIFF, LZW, climate data

I. INTRODUCTION

To improve access to climatological data and accelerate research requiring this data in Hawai'i, the Hawai'i Climate Data Portal (HCDP) [1], [2] was created. The HCDP provides public access to climatological data collected by sensor stations throughout the state, as well as derived data products and visualizations. The primary derived data product provided by the HCDP is a set of gridded data maps representing estimated statewide values at a 250m x 250m resolution. These maps are available for rainfall, temperature, and normalized difference vegetation index, with additional variables in development. These are generated by an automated workflow at a daily and monthly timescale and include 30+ years of historical data.

The Tag Image File Format (TIFF) is a file format commonly used to store raster graphic images – images stored as a matrix of values. The GeoTIFF format is an extension to this that allows for georeferencing data to be stored in the images metadata. This provides a good way to store and display gridded data over a geographical region. GeoTIFFs are used to store climatological data for the HCDP.

Since the HCDP contains a large amount of data over a period of time, it is useful to be able to construct a timeseries representation of the data. While this is relatively straightforward for the sensor station data, which has a relatively limited number of data points which are stored in a database, the ability to view timeseries of "virtual stations" - arbitrary points on the map - is more complicated. This will potentially require processing a very large number of the GeoTIFF files the data is stored in. As such, a method conducive to providing

these timeseries to a user without excessive delay requires an efficient method for extracting the values.

This timeseries generator is integrated into an application programming interface (API) [3] that backs the HCDP. The API is set up to index the GeoTIFF data files and can pull a list of files for a given dataset and time period. A TIFF extraction program was created to take this set of files and efficiently generate a timeseries of the data for an index in the gridded data or geographical location. This project is open source and the code can be found at https://github.com/HCDP/geotiff_extract.

II. BACKGROUND

A number of libraries for handling TIFF and GeoTiff files exist such as `tiff` [4] for python and the `geotiff.js` [5] and `tiff.js` [6] libraries for JavaScript. These are general purpose libraries and will generally read all of the data in a TIFF file and package it into a class for easy handling. This is great if trying to render the data or manage it in a reusable fashion; however, reading all of the data in a file has a large memory and computational overhead, particularly if the data is compressed.

Lower-level libraries such as `libtiff` [7] for C++ also exist. `Libtiff` has the advantage of providing a strip-oriented reading method which allows specific strips to be read. While this is a great improvement over the aforementioned libraries that read and decompress all of the data, with the added advantage of being implemented in a compiled language, it is possible to further speed up this process by decompressing partial strips of data. A further advantage of a specialized library is that it can be very lightweight.

Since decompressing the data composes the majority of the computational overhead of pulling values from a compressed TIFF file, optimizations to this process can have a large benefit to the overall time needed to pull values over a large number of files. To support this ability, a specialized method for extracting an index from the compressed files was developed.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

This TIFF value extractor was implemented in c++ as a header only library. This was designed to support TIFF files using Lempel-Ziv-Welch (LZW) compression, one of the most widely used compression types for TIFF files. The library is broken into two main components, a `Reader` class that

extracts the necessary data from the file and a Decoder class that handles decoding the LZW compressed data strip.

A. Reader Class

TIFF files are broken into three logical components, the Image File Header (IFH), Image File Directory (IFD), and the image data [8]. The IFH contains some basic information about the file and the file offset for the first IFD. The Reader will read this header to verify the file is valid and then move to the location of the first IFD.

The IFD contains a header indicating the number of entries in the IFD, followed by a set of entries containing tagged values. For the purposes of value extraction, only four values from this section are needed, the map width and height, the offsets for the data strips, and the strip byte counts. The Reader will scan the IFD for these tags and break after getting the required data.

The gridded map data in the TIFF file is stored in strips. Each row of values is considered a strip. These strips may not be stored in a contiguous block of data and have variable lengths when compressed. The strip offset entry in the IFD contains a set of file offsets where each strip is located, while the strip byte counts contains a set of values indicating the size of these strips. This provides all the information needed to read the strip of data containing the requested value. The Reader reads this data strip into a buffer and passes it to the Decoder along with the column of the value being requested.

B. Decoder Class

The LZW decoder is modeled on the decoder used by the python Tiff file library with an important modification. The decoder relies on and builds out a code table for decoding values as it goes. This is built as normal, but the decoded data itself will be ignored until the desired value is reached. Once the value being extracted has been decoded, the Decoder can terminate without decompressing the remaining portion of the data strip. This will result in a variable speed up depending on what column the value being extracted falls in, but the effects can be relatively large particularly for locations close to the left edge of the map, since this decompression is the primary source of computational overhead.

C. Driver

Since the primary purpose for creating this efficient TIFF value extractor is to quickly pull values from a large number of TIFF files, a driver program was also created leveraging this library. The driver takes a set of TIFF files and the requested value index as command line argument, which are provided to the Reader. OpenMP [9] is used to parallelize this process, allowing for a number of files to be processed at once. OpenMP utilizes an internal thread pool to divide the work over an optimal number of threads and is very easy to integrate into the driver program. It uses a pragma compiler directive system allowing the loop handling the calls to the Reader to be parallelized in one line.

Ultimately, this driver code is designed to be integrated into the HCDP API, which will call this as a subprocess and use the

Index 0	Index 1143	Index 2287
2.08ms	2.15ms	2.33ms

TABLE I
THE AVERAGE TIME TAKEN FOR THE FIRST, MIDDLE, AND LAST INDEX TO BE EXTRACTED OF A SINGLE FILE.

	Index 0	Index 1143	Index 2287
With Threading	112.83ms	206.36ms	233.64ms
Without Threading	171.41ms	347.21ms	389.36ms

TABLE II
THE AVERAGE TIME TAKEN FOR THE FIRST, MIDDLE, AND LAST INDEX TO BE EXTRACTED OF 400 FILES WITH AND WITHOUT THREADING ENABLED.

results to construct a timeseries of the values. To accommodate this usage, this driver program takes the values and outputs them to stdout in the same order as the files were provided as a space separated list. In the event that any of the TIFF reader functions fail, an underscore is output instead of a value. This output can then be handled by the API and parsed into a JavaScript object notation (JSON) object to be returned to the caller.

IV. RESULTS

The extraction code was tested on the machine running the HCDP API directly. This machine has an Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2687W v3 @3.10GHz which has 2 cores. The data files this was tested against have a width of 2288 columns, so the tests were run on column 0, 1143, and 2287 to test the speedup achieved by the partial decompression. At column 2287 the entire strip is decompressed, so this will be analogous to implementations such as the libtiff strip reader that read and decode a single strip. Tests were done on an input of a single file (Table I) as well as on 400 files with multithreading enabled and disabled (Table II). A sample size of 400 was selected since this roughly matches the number of months stored by the data portal’s monthly data sets. All tests were averaged over 100 executions.

The tests demonstrated a significant speedup for values at the beginning of a strip vs at the end, with the elements at index 0 taking less than half the time of the last element in the 400 file test, though there does seem to be a more significant speedup at lower indices. Additionally, the threading made a significant improvement in the runtime, with greater improvements being possible if this machine were allocated additional CPUs.

V. HCDP INTERFACE INTEGRATION

The API endpoint leveraging this GeoTIFF extraction process was integrated into the HCDP’s user interface to generate visualizations of the timeseries of values for climatological variables at any location in Hawai’i. This allows users to select an arbitrary map location and create a “virtual station”. The location of this virtual station is sent as a query to the API along with information about the climatological variable being viewed, and a timeseries of data at this location for the lifespan

Fig. 1. A timeseries graph of gridded maximum temperature data provided by the HCDP. This data is produced from the gridded GeoTIFF products derived from sensor station data. This data is generated and returned by the GeoTIFF processing endpoint in the HCDP API.

of the dataset is returned. Most of the variables measured are at a daily and monthly timescale. Timeseries for both of these scales are requested and made available to the user.

While the TIFF extraction process described is able to pull values relatively quickly, very large queries can still take some time to process. For example, daily data over the lifespan of a dataset going back to 1990 – the range of many of the HCDP datasets – must index and process over 12,000 files. To improve the responsiveness of the interface and user experience, large queries are separated into multiple chunks. This way data can be loaded into the timeseries visualization as it is received rather than requiring all of the data to be loaded at once. This has the additional benefit of allowing some chunks of a query to be cancelled if a user selects a different location before all of the data from one is complete. The web application throttles the number of requests that are sent to the API at the same time and has a queue of remaining query chunks that can be cancelled before being issued. Single large queries issued to the API whenever a user selects a new location could generate increased load on the API and underlying file system since there is no way to halt an API request once issued.

Once the data is returned to the user it is loaded into a set of interactive graphs for each timescale (Figure 1). Graphs are generated using Plotly.js [10] and have the built-in ability to rescale and manipulate the graph view as well as produce and download an image of the graph. Users can download the timeseries data for the location as a comma separated value (CSV) file containing timestamp and value columns for additional analysis without requiring API access.

VI. FUTURE WORK

Currently, this implementation has some limitations. Notably, it only handles files with little endian byte order that use LZW compression or no compression. LZW compression will generally be the most common compression particularly for applications that require a lossless algorithm such as the intended use case for this project; however, it would be useful to extend this to handle other compression algorithms, such as deflate.

Given the intended use case of extracting a value from the same index of GeoTIFF files with the same spatial extent, a further heuristic could be implemented in the case that part of the strips contain background no-data values for a portion of the leading edge of the data. It would be possible to partially decompress the strip from one of the files up to the first real value and begin at that point for the rest of the files, sharing the decompression table state at that position. Assuming all of the files use the same no-data value, the decompression up to this point will be identical; so, this should allow subsequent files to further limit the amount of data they need to decompress.

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